

Interview Guide

Warm-up / Background

- Could you briefly describe your professional background and your work with oil paintings on canvas?
- How do you currently approach assessing or, where possible, anticipating the aging of artworks? What tools or methods do you currently use?

Current Practices & Needs

- What challenges do you face when trying to anticipate or communicate aging effects?
- In an ideal scenario, what kind of support or tools would make your work easier or more effective?

Usefulness

- How do you think a (VR) tool that simulates the aging of oil paintings could be useful in your work?
- In what existing conservation practices, if any, would you see yourself using such a tool?

Adoption & Integration

- Which features or capabilities would encourage you to adopt this kind of tool in your workflow?
- What barriers might prevent you from using it?

Risks

- What concerns or risks would you associate with using an interactive (VR-based) aging simulation tool? Could it be misleading or problematic?
- How might reliance on such a tool affect professional judgment or decision-making?

Trust & Trustworthiness

- What would make you trust the results produced by a VR aging simulation?
- What factors might reduce your trust in such a tool?

Co-Design & Feedback

- Is there anything else you think developers should consider when creating such a tool?